

OrganKits project

OrganKits partners have several updates to share!

The last activities of our project are presented in this 6th newsletter.

Want to find more?

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Top stories

International Conference on OrganKits

On 27–28 May, the International Conference on OrganKits took place bringing together the project's seven partners alongside one of the associated educational secondary schools...

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OrganKits Workshop on Health and Well-Being at Science Museums

Understanding health and well-being goes far beyond memorizing anatomical facts — it requires real engagement with the body and its systems, especially when these concepts intersect with everyday challenges and lifestyles.

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OrganKits Video Series Surpasses 2,000 Views

The OrganKits project has reached a new milestone in its dissemination efforts, with its collection of seven promotional videos surpassing 2,175 total views across platforms.

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Permanent OrganKits Exhibition at the Museo de la Ciencia y el Agua, Murcia

From 15 May to 15 September, the Museo de la Ciencia y el Agua in Murcia is hosting a permanent exhibition on the OrganKits project.

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